

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Measuring Thermal Properties Under Cryogenic Conditions

The following Application Highlight features the use of the FLEX Transient Plane Source method in thermal conductivity testing under cryogenic conditions.

One of the most common variables investigated in thermal characterization is how a material's properties change as a function of temperature. Thermal conductivity is highly relevant for this characterization interest as it directly quantifies a material's ability to conduct heat. Ambient temperatures suffice for basic material testing, and many options exist to satisfy those needs. However, when pushing the limits of material testing at extreme temperatures, there is significantly more complexity in the test setups as well as more limited options that accommodate the inherent requirements. While more challenging, it is often at these extremes where materials will begin to behave atypically and thus the need for direct test data is mandatory as many trends and assumptions do not hold under these conditions. This is especially important for applications in the cryogenic range such as cold chain storage, aerospace, and manufacturing.

Figure 1. Cold Chain Storage Transport (left) and Trident with TPS Sensor (right).

C-Therm's Trident platform offers multiple transient-based methods suited to various materials and test conditions (i.e. temperature, pressure, humidity, etc.). Herein we discuss the use of the FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method in the characterization of materials under cryogenic conditions (approx. -200°C). Figure 2 below illustrates results obtained on an AISI 304 Stainless Steel. Measurements were compared to the provided reference values, and all were found to be within 5% of the expected results.

Thermal Conductivity Results of AISI 304 Stainless Steel

Figure 2. Thermal Conductivity of AISI 304 SS Under Cryogenic Conditions.

The thermal conductivity of ice was also under cryogenic conditions was also investigated. To prepare the samples, deionized water was first sonicated and sparged with inert gas before freezing at a slow rate. It should be noted that due to the inherent nature of water during freezing, odd behaviours (i.e. non-uniform crystallization patterns) are commonly observed close to 0°C, and overall measurements are highly subject to the quality of the prepared sample (impurities, cracks, bubbles, etc., can all result in an increased variation). Results from testing were compared to multiple reference sources containing theoretical calculations and expected trends. As can be seen in Figure 3, the results obtained matched closely with theoretical results down to -50°C and agreed with the general trend expected approaching -200°C.

Thermal Conductivity Results of Ice

Figure 3. Thermal Conductivity of Ice Under Cryogenic Conditions.

In summary, the thermal conductivity characterization of a material is significantly affected by temperature. While basic systems offer various options for rudimentary testing, extreme conditions demand specialized capabilities beyond their technical compatibility. Notably, the FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method available on the Trident platform enables efficient testing under cryogenic conditions. The results obtained serve as a valuable solution for assessing materials used in a variety of cryogenic applications.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com